

Using CLIP to extract and analyze images of the family in 3,000 Dutch-language children's books, 1800-1940.

Short paper

Dr. Thomas Smits, University of Antwerp, @thomassmits 0000-0001-8579-824X
Paavo van der Eecken, MA, University of Antwerp, 0000-0001-9494-8932
Prof. dr. Vanessa Joosen, University of Antwerp, 0000-0001-8060-5728

While adult fiction is frequently centered on a single protagonist, books for children often revolve around the interaction between a child and family. Alston (2008) argues that this aspect defines *children's* literature. The family provides the background of the story and often shapes the narrative, with stories relating domestic bliss, conflicts in the family, or the sorrow of losing a (grand)parent or sibling (Ghesquière & Joosen 2014; Wesseling 2021). While the social make-up of families changed in the last fifty years, Alston (2008) notes that, over the last two centuries, the representation of the family in children's literature is marked by stark continuity rather than change. She describes this as a tenacious 'disciplinary discourse' (Foucault, 1969) that reproduces conservative family values.

Alston bases her analysis on a close reading of several canonical texts. However, books for children frequently contain text and illustrations. Images have in fact been demonstrated to make a stronger and longer lasting impression on young readers (Waller, 2019). This paper discusses the first step in a larger research project that uses computational techniques to analyze the multimodal representation of the family in the ~3,000 digitized Dutch-language children's books (1800-1940) of the DBNL. We present a method that applies the multimodal machine learning (ML) model CLIP to classify images of families from the total 38,363 images in this corpus.

Scholars of children's literature have noted that 'the family' is a slippery concept (Wesseling 2021). Concerning images, the wide range of possible (combinations of) family members, family activities, and settings make it impossible to train traditional computer vision (CV) models to classify images of the family. The multimodal model CLIP (Radford et al., 2021) provides a solution to this problem. Trained on 400.000.000 image/text pairs, CLIP learns visual concepts from language. In contrast to CV models, CLIP does not require annotated data or task-specific training: it can find visual matches for an extremely large number of textual prompts. However, this 'zero-shot' capability leads to a methodological pitfall: the lack of (need for) annotated data makes it hard to inspect the performance of the model. We propose to inspect the performance of CLIP on our specific classification task by manually annotating a set of images that were returned for three different prompts (see below).

Method

Several scholars have applied computational methods to study children’s literature (Griffin, 2018; Haverals & Geybels, 2021). Directly connected to our approach, Helm et al. (2019) and Mandl et al. (2020) used CV models to study the ‘iconography’ of children’s books. As noted above, traditional CV models are unable to identify complex visual concepts. Therefore, we rely on CLIP’s zero-shot classification and introduce three prompts to identify images of families in our corpus: ‘a family’ (PR1), ‘an image of a family’ (PR2), and ‘an illustration of a family’ (PR3). CLIP connects images to a prompt by returning the n images that display the top n cosine similarity scores $[-1,1]$. Cosine similarity is used to determine if two different items display similarity. For our classification task, the methodological problem lies in determining the optimal value of n . When does a certain cosine similarity score no longer indicate a meaningful result (an image of a family)? We approach this problem by manually annotating a set of 6939 images that were returned by CLIP for our three prompts with $n=5000$.¹ We calculate the precision of CLIP for every 100 images.

Figure 1. Average precision and range precision per 100 top- n images

Results

With $n=5000$, CLIP extracted 1692 correct images for PR1, 1712 for PR2, and 1654 for PR3. Following a suggestion of Radford et al. (2021), we note that the precision of the model increases if we add contextual information to a prompt (image of/illustration of). Figure 1 shows that the precision of the model is relatively high for the first 100 images but drops afterwards. This suggests that CLIP has a concept of what a family should look like but that it has more trouble with images that deviate from this typical representation. However, the model also continues to correctly identify images (between 20-30%) when nearing $n=5000$. This makes clear that, with our current method, the model cannot be trusted to provide a complete subset of images containing a family in a larger corpus.

¹ We determined that images are of a family when they depict at least two different generations, so (grand)parent and child. We thank our intern Catherine Cuyper for helping us annotate the dataset.

Figure 2. Top-8 images for PR2 ‘an image of a family’

Qualitatively inspecting the performance of the model tells us a lot about CLIP’s concept of a family. For example, we notice recurring themes in the images that were correctly identified: father, mother, several children, often sitting at a table or next to a bed (Figure 2). CLIP also returns families of all sorts of animals (Figure 3), which demonstrates the benefit of learning visual concepts from image/text combinations (multimodal ML) rather than from visual features only (traditional CV). We also learn from common mistakes. CLIP frequently classified images of girls caring for young(er) children (without parents) as images of the family. Similarly, we often come across girls playing with dolls (Figure 4). CLIP failed to learn the difference between mother/girl, but it might have learned the performative aspects of family life (children ‘playing’ mother and father). These common mistakes represent the same conservative family discourse as the correctly identified images. This not only points to the pervasive nature of this discourse but also adds to analyses of the family in children’s books: children are not just cared for, but frequently assume caring roles themselves (whether for younger siblings or in play).

Figure 3. Images of animal families correctly identified by CLIP

Figure 4. Mislabeled images of girls caring for young(er) children and playing with dolls.

Conclusion

Without the need for annotation or task-specific training, CLIP can be used to easily study visual representation at scale. In contrast to other CV models, CLIP's multimodal nature enables it to identify complex visual concepts. In the future, we hope to apply it to more abstract concepts, such as home, love, or innocence. However, using CLIP also comes with a set of specific methodological problems. Most prominently, the lack of need for annotated training data makes it hard to interpret the

performance of the model. Our method, which provides some insights into the performance of the model, shows that standardized practices are needed to properly assess the performance of CLIP.

Bibliography.

Alston, A. (2008). *The Family in English Children's Literature*. Routledge.

Foucault, M. (1969). *L'archéologie du savoir*. Gallimard.

Ghesquière, R., Joosen, V. (2014). Van de kleine naar de grote wereld: Gezinsboeken en schoolverhalen. In: R. Ghesquière, V. Joosen, H. van Lierop-Debrauwer (Eds), *Een land van waan en wijs: Geschiedenis van de Nederlandse jeugdliteratuur* (pp. 311-343). Atlas Contact.

Griffin, M. (2018). Once Upon a Genre: Distant Reading, the Newbery Medal, and the Affordances of Interdisciplinary Paradigms for Understanding Children's Literature. *Graduate Theses and Dissertations*.

Haverals, W., & Geybels, L. (2021). Putting the Sorting Hat on J.K. Rowling's Reader: A digital inquiry into the age of the implied readership of the Harry Potter series. *Journal of Cultural Analytics*, 6(1), 24077. <https://doi.org/10.22148/001c.24077>

Helm, W., Mandl, T., Putjenter, S., Schmideler, S., & Zellhöfer, D. (2019). *Distant Viewing-Forschung mit digitalisierten Kinderbüchern: Voraussetzungen, Herausforderungen und Ansätze*. 7.

Mandl, T., Im, C., Helm, W., & Schmideler, S. (2020). Object Recognition in Illustrated Children Books: Challenges of Applying Computer Vision Systems. *Book of Abstracts of the Digital Humanities in the Nordic Countries 5th Conference. Riga, 20–23 October 2020*.

Radford, A., Kim, J. W., Hallacy, C., Ramesh, A., Goh, G., Agarwal, S., Sastry, G., Aspell, A., Mishkin, P., Clark, J., Krueger, G., & Sutskever, I. (2021). Learning Transferable Visual Models From Natural Language Supervision. *ArXiv:2103.00020 [Cs]*. <http://arxiv.org/abs/2103.00020>

Waller, A. (2019). *Rereading Childhood Books A Poetics*. Bloomsbury Academic.

Wesseling, L. (2021). Family. In P. Nel, L. Paul, & N. Christensen (Eds.), *Keywords for children's literature* (Vol. 9, pp. 74–77). NYU Press.